

Non-Destructive, Self-Contained Extraction Method of Parasitic Resistance in HEMT Devices

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Abstract

This contribution addresses the classical problem of determining the extrinsic resistances (R_G , R_S and R_D) of field-effect transistors (FETs), and in particular of high-electron mobility transistors (HEMTs). The presented approach relies on small-signal measurements of open-channel transistors, as often proposed both for traditional metal-semiconductor FETs (MESFETs) and HEMTs. Unlike what is common practice with HEMTs, the method proposed here does not oversimplify the model of the active channel. On the contrary, the Authors retrieve from the literature a possible analytical model for the open-channel HEMT and use it to determine the triplet of extrinsic resistances without the need of stressing the gate junction with too high currents. Another result of the approach, valid both for MESFETs and HEMTs, is a deterministic way to remove the contribution of the gate junction from the small-signal parameters of the measured devices.

All extractions process data which are available on suitable ranges in frequency or in bias voltage, without taking to the limit the sweep parameters or seeking specific resonances. Also, optimizations are only allowed to refine the nominal values, not as the main technique of extraction. These goals are achieved by setting up different subproblems in the form of over-determined linear systems and then solving by pseudo-inversion. The validity of the approach is demonstrated on measurements of devices from advanced HEMT technologies realized by OMMIC, both GaAs-based (40 nm gate length) and GaN-based (100 nm and 60 nm).

Keywords: Extrinsic circuit, HEMT, parasitic resistances, small-signal equivalent circuit (SSEC).

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1 Introduction

One of the classical problems in the extraction of small-signal equivalent-circuit (SSEC) models for field-effect transistors (FETs) lies in accurately determining the device parasitic resistances. The first methods proposed, focusing on GaAs MESFETs, were based on DC measurements of the devices in cold region ($V_{DS} \approx 0$ V). The most important of those methods, based on measuring ‘end’ resistances, were backed by a theory representing the channel as a distributed diode at $I_G \approx 0$ mA [1–3] or $I_G \geq 0$ mA [4]. The number of equations obtained with these approaches were not always sufficient to solve for all unknowns separately. Also, different setup configurations were necessary which, although appropriate for discrete devices, do not chime with monolithic ones.

To simplify the setup and improve consistency of the extracted resistances with RF data, approaches based on S-parameters were then developed which are now classic [5, 6]. Focused on MESFET devices, these works often resort to assumptions which do not transfer to HEMTs, with particular reference to the dependence of the channel resistance R_{ch} on the operating point. A lot of more recent contributions specifically targeting HEMTs, on the contrary, seem to aim at by-passing this issue by biasing the transistors at high forward gate voltages, so as to minimize the channel resistance [7–11]. However, there is no warrant that R_{ch} is negligible as compared to the parasitic resistances. Also, overdoing with forward bias may damage the device irreversibly.

Other contributions approach the lack of equations with which modelers have traditionally struggled with by making additional assumptions based on experience and good sense [12] or by proposing simplified models [13]. In particular, notice that the coefficients multiplying R_{ch} in the model of the unbiased FET in [13] are different from those derived with the more rigorous approach in [5].

Finally, some have proposed optimization-based approaches to extract the parasitic resistances and, at the same time, the whole extrinsic circuit [14] or even the complete SSEC [15]. In other cases, the extrinsic circuit has been derived from EM simulations [16] or not computed at all, treating the device as a black box [17]. Black-box characterizations, however, cannot be extrapolated in frequency nor be equipped with noise models, unless these also are black-box [16, 18]. Noise models, nevertheless, are customarily in the form of SSECs with equivalent noise temperatures and require a precise determination of the resistive elements [15, 19].

In this paper, the generalities of the open-channel FET model are first reappraised in Section 2 from [5]. Then, in Section 3 a novel technique is presented to get rid of the contribution of the series diode appearing in the input impedance, so as to leave a simple T-network (comprising only the parasitics and R_{ch} -related terms) for subsequent processing. Finally, in Section 4 a physical model of R_{ch} is adopted from the literature to allow a full characterization of the channel at safe forward biases.

As usual, the techniques presented in this work require the extraction of constant parameters in order to fit the underlying models to measurement data. However, all of them rely on deterministic extractions rather than brute-force optimization. This is achieved by extensive use of pseudo-inversion applied to over-determined linear systems of equations [20]. In the remainder of this paper, whenever a problem is cast in the matrix form $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x}$, the solution \mathbf{x} follows directly and is not explicitly declared. It is also implicitly assumed that the number of rows of the system is at least equal to the

number of unknowns, n . For readability's sake, linear systems will be presented not in their entirety but in the form $b_i = [a_{i,1} \cdots a_{i,n}] \cdot [x_1 \cdots x_n]^T$, i.e., by referring to the generic i -th row.

2 Open-channel FET model

The operating condition here chosen for parasitic resistance extraction is at open channel, i.e. $V'_{DS} \approx 0$ V, $V'_{GS} > V_T$, where the apex denotes the intrinsic device and V_T is the threshold voltage. Moreover, gate current is kept very low ($I_G \approx 0$ mA) so that $V'_{GS} \approx V_{GS}$ and $V'_{DS} \approx V_{DS}$.

Following the approach originally proposed in [5], the channel of the FET is modeled as a lossy transmission line. As opposed to [5], however, the parallel portion of this line comprises both a capacitive (C_j) and a resistive ($R_j = 1/G_j$) component. The series portion is considered purely resistive (R_{ch}). Thus the secondary parameters (propagation constant and characteristic impedance, respectively) of the line result to be:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{l} \sqrt{R_{ch} \cdot (G_j + j\omega C_j)} \quad (1)$$

$$Z_c = \sqrt{\frac{R_{ch}}{G_j + j\omega C_j}} = \frac{\gamma l}{G_j + j\omega C_j} \quad (2)$$

with $\omega = 2\pi f$, f the frequency and l the channel length. Thus, standard theory on transmission lines yields the impedance matrix of the channel from (1)-(2). This matrix is clearly passive and reciprocal, the latter feature making it convenient to represent it as a T-network. Thus, the three branches of the T-network are easily reorganized to set the intrinsic source terminal as the common node of the intrinsic circuit. The resulting impedance matrix is:

$$\mathbf{Z}' = Z_c \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\cosh(\gamma l)}{\sinh(\gamma l)} & \frac{\cosh(\gamma l) - 1}{\sinh(\gamma l)} \\ \frac{\cosh(\gamma l) - 1}{\sinh(\gamma l)} & 2 \frac{\cosh(\gamma l) - 1}{\sinh(\gamma l)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Provided that $|\gamma l| \approx 0$, this can be approximated as follows:

$$\mathbf{Z}' \approx \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{G_j + j\omega C_j} + \frac{1}{3} R_{ch} & \frac{1}{2} R_{ch} \\ \frac{1}{2} R_{ch} & R_{ch} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

from which the equivalent circuit boxed in Fig. 1 is derived. Since (4) is passive, so is the corresponding circuit representation, notwithstanding the curious term $-1/6 R_{ch}$. This element, resulting from approximating a distributed model, is in any case inaccessible from outside the intrinsic circuit.

Adding the series parasitic elements yields:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{Z}' + \begin{bmatrix} R_G + R_S & R_S \\ R_S & R_D + R_S \end{bmatrix} + j\omega \cdot \begin{bmatrix} L_G + L_S & L_S \\ L_S & L_D + L_S \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

which, for $|\gamma l| \approx 0$, corresponds to the models used in [7–11]. Considering the parasitic capacitances C_{pg} , C_{pd} and C_{pgd} in the configuration adopted in [5] would impact somewhat on (4), except for the Z_{22} term. However, C_{pg} and C_{pd} are placed differently in different models. In this contribution, the parasitic capacitances are simply neglected for the sake of resistance extraction: see Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Equivalent circuit model of a FET at open channel.

It is interesting to observe that the coefficients of the R_{ch} terms appearing in \mathbf{Z}' are the same as those derived from the DC analysis aimed at supporting the end-resistance technique [1–4]. This is reasonable since the drain terminal of the basic configuration is kept floating in both the DC and RF analyses. However, the RF approach does not require that the device be actually terminated in an open circuit: this condition is ensured mathematically by converting from S-parameters to Z-parameters. As a convenient consequence, the same power supply settings can be used for cold measurements ($V_{DS} = 0$ V) as for hot measurements (saturation region), and the DC resistances of the bias and supply circuits are automatically corrected for. Also, inconsistencies due to using different equipments (multimeters or VNAs) for the resistance extraction are avoided.

As a last remark, it is here noted that the actual steps followed to derive the low-frequency resistances of the \mathbf{Z} have an impact on subsequent computations. This is

especially true when dealing with the Z_{11} parameter, where the resistive part $R_{11} = \text{Re}[Z_{11}]$ shows significant dependence on frequency as a consequence of the series diode. Also, typically this resistance takes on values much higher than $R_{12} = \text{Re}[Z_{12}]$ and $R_{22} = \text{Re}[Z_{22}]$, for the same reason. Therefore, rather than extracting the low-frequency resistive circuit from the Z-parameters (T-network), it is sometimes more convenient (depending on personal judgment and quality of the data) to use the Y-parameters, which have a more regular behavior and are almost constant over acceptably broad bandwidths near DC. In this case, to further broaden the frequency range feasible for the extraction, the DC values of the associated Π -network can be derived as the constant term of a quadratic polynomial (of the form $G(f) = G_0 + G_1 f + G_2 f^2$) rather than as a simple average over frequency. To determine G_0 , G_1 and G_2 , a linear system is easily set up:

$$[G]_i = [1 \quad f \quad f^2]_i \cdot \begin{bmatrix} G_0 \\ G_1 \\ G_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

with i denoting here the i -th measurement frequency.

3 Removal of the gate junction

The parallel of G_j and C_j in the open-channel FET model basically represents a junction in moderately forward bias. If this junction could be removed from the measured parameters, a simple T-network would result, suitable for an immediate identification of the remaining elements. In [7–9, 11], several methods are proposed to identify the necessary parameters of the gate junction. These require restricting the focus on specific frequencies or frequency ranges, to subsequently extract the element values from the real and imaginary parts of the network functions, or derivatives thereof. In this Section, however, it will be shown that the junction parameters can be easily identified while considering the whole frequency range measured (as long as the effects of C_{pg} , C_{pd} and C_{pgd} remain negligible, of course).

To that end, the low-frequency approximation $|\gamma l| \approx 0$ is assumed, so that:

$$Z_{11} = R_{sum} + \frac{R_j}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} + j\omega \cdot \left(L_{sum} - \tau \frac{R_j}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$R_{sum} = R_G + R_S + \frac{1}{3} R_{ch} \quad (8)$$

$$L_{sum} = L_G + L_S \quad (9)$$

$$\tau = R_j C_j \quad (10)$$

In the first step, τ and $\tau R_{sum} + L_{sum}$ are computed by pseudo-inversion. This can be done after recognizing that the diode-related rational term appears both in

$R_{11} = \text{Re}[Z_{11}]$ and in $X_{11} = \text{Im}[Z_{11}]$:

$$\omega\tau \frac{R_j}{1 + \omega^2\tau^2} = \omega\tau \cdot (R_{11} - R_{sum}) \quad (11)$$

$$= \omega L_{sum} - X_{11} \quad (12)$$

so that the following linear system results from equating the right-hand terms and recasting:

$$[X_{11}]_i = \begin{bmatrix} -\omega R_{11} & \omega \\ & \tau \\ \tau R_{sum} & + L_{sum} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (13)$$

where the subscript i denotes the i -th frequency. For future use, let the second solution be assigned a symbol:

$$k = \tau R_{sum} + L_{sum} \quad (14)$$

Second, since τ is now known, R_{sum} and R_j can be computed by another pseudo-inversion from R_{11} :

$$[R_{11} \cdot (1 + \omega^2\tau^2)]_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \omega^2\tau^2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}_i \cdot \begin{bmatrix} R_{sum} \\ R_j \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where the subscript i denotes again the i -th frequency.

Finally, the remaining terms C_j and L_{sum} are straightforwardly computed as:

$$L_{sum} = k - \tau R_{sum} \quad (16)$$

$$C_j = \frac{\tau}{R_j} \quad (17)$$

It is worth noting that deriving L_{sum} is a useful by-product of the proposed procedure. Indeed, whereas L_S and $L_D + L_S$ can be directly computed from $\text{Im}[Z_{12}]$ and $\text{Im}[Z_{22}]$, respectively, the same does not hold for $L_G + L_S$ due to the presence of the series diode. However, (16) provides the missing equation for $L_G + L_S$, thus allowing to determine the full triplet of parasitic inductances.

As a check of the consistency of the extractions, one should obtain an approximately constant value of L_{sum} from measurements at different V'_{GS} values. Also, it is possible to verify whether the extracted R_j follows the classical exponential law as a function of V'_{GS} . Start from the diode law between I_G and V'_{GS} :

$$I_G = I_0 \cdot \left(e^{V'_{GS}/\eta V_{th}} - 1 \right) \quad (18)$$

with η the ideality factor and $V_{th} = k_B T/q$. As usual, k_B denotes the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, q the elementary positive charge. Then, $G_j = R_j^{-1}$ is found to be:

$$G_j = \frac{\partial I_G}{\partial V_G} = \frac{I_0}{\eta V_{th}} \cdot e^{V'_{GS}/\eta V_{th}} \quad (19)$$

The two unknowns, I_0 and η , are easily computed after converting to natural logarithms and applying another pseudo-inversion:

$$[\ln(G_j \cdot 1 \Omega)]_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & V'_{GS} \\ \ln\left(\frac{I_0}{\eta V_{th}^1} \cdot 1 \Omega\right) \\ \frac{1}{\eta V_{th}} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (20)$$

where the subscript i denotes the i -th measurement at fixed V'_{GS} . Unlike more traditional approaches, no limits for high V'_{GS} are necessary, since a perfectly exponential law is obtained when considering the derivative $\partial I_G / \partial V_G$.

4 Channel modeling and extraction of R_G , R_S , R_D

In the limit for $V_{GS} \rightarrow \infty$, the channel resistance should become negligible as compared to R_G , R_S and R_D , which on the contrary are bias-independent. For this reason, several works [7–9, 11] assume that the gate can be enough forward-biased to approximate the channel as a short circuit. This corresponds to using $R_{ch} = 0 \Omega$ in (4). However, applying too high gate voltages could result in excessive gate currents and, in turn, irreversible damage caused to the device: this is to be avoided especially when subsequent tests are to be carried out, such as noise characterization.

The stress associated with high forward bias can be avoided if a model of the channel dependency on bias is known. Indeed, this would allow to fit the model parameters to measurements in a bias range where the device operates safely. Then, the model could be used in an extended range if necessary.

As mentioned in [5], the R_{ch} of MESFETs with flat-doping profiles can be modeled following [21] as:

$$R_{ch} = \frac{R_{ch,m}}{1 - \sqrt{\alpha}} \quad (21)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{V'_{GS} - V_{bi}}{V_T - V_{bi}} \quad (22)$$

where V_{bi} is the built-in junction potential, V_T is the threshold voltage and $R_{ch,m}$ is a constant.

In the case of HEMT devices, however, a different model should be used. Following [22, 23], in particular, R_{ch} of HEMTs is here represented in the ohmic region as:

$$R_{ch} = \frac{R_{ch,h}}{V'_{GS} - V_T} \quad (23)$$

where $R_{ch,h}$ is a constant depending on device realization. With this model, the total output resistance can be expressed as:

$$R_{22} = R_S + R_D + R_{ch} = a_{22} + \frac{b_{22}}{V'_{GS} + c_{22}} \quad (24)$$

The parameters $a_{22} = R_S + R_D$, $b_{22} = R_{ch,h}$ and $c_{22} = -V_T$ can be determined by pseudo-inversion from measurements at different V'_{GS} (associated with low I_G values). In particular, the problem can easily be cast in linear form as follows:

$$R_{22} \cdot (V'_{GS} + c_{22}) = a_{22} \cdot (V'_{GS} + c_{22}) + b_{22} \quad (25)$$

$$[R_{22}V'_{GS}]_i = \begin{bmatrix} V'_{GS} & 1 & -R_{22} \end{bmatrix}_i \cdot \begin{bmatrix} a_{22} \\ b_{22} + a_{22}c_{22} \\ c_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

where the subscript i denotes again the i -th measurement at fixed V'_{GS} . After solving for a_{22} , $b_{22} + a_{22}c_{22}$ and c_{22} , b_{22} is straightforwardly computed.

Notice that, in theory, a similar procedure could be applied to $R_{sum} = R_G + R_S + 1/3R_{ch}$ and $R_{12} = R_S + 1/2R_{ch}$, yielding comparable values of the channel parameters. Then, the constant terms resulting from the R_{sum} -, R_{12} - and R_{22} -based fittings (a_{sum} , a_{12} and a_{22} , respectively) would allow to set up the following system of equations:

$$a_{sum} = R_G + R_S \quad (27)$$

$$a_{12} = R_S \quad (28)$$

$$a_{22} = R_D + R_S \quad (29)$$

from which the extrinsic resistances are easily obtained. However, as mentioned above, the reliability of the R_{22} parameter is inherently superior to the other two, which in fact may produce unsound fittings in some cases.

As a safer procedure, the Authors suggest fitting the channel resistance model to R_{22} measurements and then inspecting the graphs of \hat{a}_{sum} and \hat{a}_{12} , defined as:

$$\hat{a}_{sum}(V'_{GS}) = R_{sum}(V'_{GS}) - 1/3R_{ch}(V'_{GS}) \quad (30)$$

$$\hat{a}_{12}(V'_{GS}) = R_{12}(V'_{GS}) - 1/2R_{ch}(V'_{GS}) \quad (31)$$

In particular, one should select the V'_{GS} range where \hat{a}_{sum} and \hat{a}_{12} are approximately constant and take their averages there. These averages, $\langle \hat{a}_{sum} \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{a}_{12} \rangle$, are good estimates of $R_G + R_S$ and R_S , respectively.

Solving the resulting system of equations yields the extrinsic resistances:

$$R_G = \langle \hat{a}_{sum} \rangle - R_S = \langle \hat{a}_{sum} \rangle - \langle \hat{a}_{12} \rangle \quad (32)$$

$$R_S = \langle \hat{a}_{12} \rangle \quad (33)$$

$$R_D = a_{22} - R_S = a_{22} - \langle \hat{a}_{12} \rangle \quad (34)$$

5 Method wrap-up

For the sake of clarity, the core of the approach presented in Sections 3-4 is summarized in the following list of steps.

1. Set $V_{DS} = 0$ V.

2. Choose safe V_{GS} sweep at open channel.
3. For each V_{GS} :
 - Measure S-parameters.
 - If possible, remove the effect of C_{PG} , C_{PD} , C_{PGD} .
 - Convert to Z-parameters to obtain $\mathbf{Z}(V'_{GS})$.
 - Extract $R_{sum}(V'_{GS})$, $R_j(V'_{GS})$, $C_j(V'_{GS})$, $L_{sum}(V'_{GS})$ by exploiting (15)-(17).
 - Remove the $G_j//C_j$ parallel from Z_{11} .
4. From $R_{22}(V'_{GS})$, extract $a_{22} = R_S + R_D$, $b_{22} = R_{ch,h}$, $c_{22} = -V_T$ by exploiting (26).
5. Compute $\hat{a}_{sum}(V'_{GS})$ and $\hat{a}_{12}(V'_{GS})$ through (30)-(31).
6. Average $\hat{a}_{sum}(V'_{GS})$ and $\hat{a}_{12}(V'_{GS})$ over the subrange where they are most constant to obtain $\langle \hat{a}_{sum} \rangle$ and $\langle \hat{a}_{12} \rangle$, respectively.
7. Solve the resulting system of equations with (32)-(34), obtaining R_G , R_D and R_S .

Since the involved currents and resistances are small, one can typically assume that $V_{GS} \approx V'_{GS}$ and $V_{DS} \approx V'_{DS}$ in the above procedure. Otherwise, the extracted resistances can be used to improve the estimates of V'_{GS} and V'_{DS} and iterate the procedure.

Notice also that the presented method does not require exploiting resistance scaling rules: on the contrary, it can be applied to a single device independently of the others. However, extracting the parasitic resistances on a multiplicity of devices (with the same unit gate width or not) can improve the overall results by statistical means.

Another parameter which one may be interested in sweeping is temperature. Indeed, up to now it was implicitly assumed that all measurements are performed at the same (or reasonably similar) temperature. On the contrary, as shown by recent literature [24,25], significant changes in physical temperature produce measurable effects on the extrinsic resistances, and especially on R_D and R_S . Clearly, this is due to the fact that R_D and R_S depend on the carrier density along semiconductor paths whereas R_G is mainly associated with metalizations.

6 Experimental validations

Before presenting the experiments, it is worth illustrating some notation. Device geometries are denoted by $N \times W_u$, N being the number of fingers and W_u the unit gate width. As opposed to W_u , total gate width is $W = N \cdot W_u$. For ease of comparison, all immittances will be normalized to a reference periphery $W_0 = 4 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$, except when otherwise noted. In particular, admittance- and impedance-type quantities are scaled by W/W_0 and W_0/W , respectively, and normalization denoted by a subscript 0.

As to the measurement of the S-parameters, these were corrected with a Line-Reflect-Reflect-Match (LRRM) calibration based on custom on-wafer cal kits, so as to completely remove the access pads and lines. The LRRM calibration was preferred to a multiline one for simplicity's sake, since it does not require a preliminary determination of the characteristic impedance. On the other hand, LRRM accuracy is limited by the validity of the (automatically determined) match model, which breaks down at high frequencies.

For the purposes of the present work, however, a relatively low portion of the measured frequency span is necessary to perform the resistance extractions, i.e., up to about 10 GHz. This range is high enough to correctly estimate the gate junction and low enough that the model in Fig. 1 is accurate.

6.1 Resistance extraction on 40 nm GaAs-based HEMT

The first experiment illustrating the proposed procedure is taken from the modeling activity of a 40-nm GaAs-based HEMT realized by OMMIC. The technology, named D004IH, is still under development by the foundry and is intended for applications in the 60-250 GHz frequency range. In this case, a $2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ device is considered.

Figure 2: $2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ device from D004IH process. Extracted $R_{11,0}$ (thick lines) with relevant fittings by pseudo-inversion (dashed lines) at $V_{DS} = 0 \text{ V}$, $V_{GS} = 0.2 \text{ V}$, 0.4 V , 0.6 V .

Figure 3: $2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ device from D004IH process. Extracted $R_{11,0}$ (thick lines) with relevant fittings by pseudo-inversion (dashed lines) at $V_{DS} = 0 \text{ V}$, $V_{GS} = 0.2 \text{ V}$, 0.4 V , 0.6 V .

The gate junction parameters are identified right away from $Z_{11,0}$ by exploiting (15)-(17), which produces fittings such as in Figs. 2-3. Then, by removing the gate junction contribution from $Z_{11,0}$ and taking the real part, $R_{sum,0}$ is obtained, as plotted in Fig. 4.

$R_{sum,0}$ can be modeled as the sum of a constant term $R_{G,0} + R_{S,0}$ and a term $R_{ch,0}$ depending on V'_{GS} , as explained in Section 4. The model parameters are determined by pseudo-inversion and refined by a least-squares algorithm: the results are signaled by cross and dot markers in the figure. Also shown is the difference between $R_{sum,0} - 1/3R_{ch,0}$, where the model of $R_{ch,0}$ is obtained from $R_{22,0}$: see Fig. 6. As expected, this difference is approximately constant, proving that the model in Section 2 is basically correct.

Figs. 5-6 show similar computations (except for removing the gate junction, of course), carried out on $R_{12,0}$ and $R_{22,0}$, respectively. Also in these two figures the thin line is derived from the model of $R_{ch,0}$ based on $R_{22,0}$.

Averaging the differences $R_{sum,0} - 1/3R_{ch,0}$, $R_{12,0} - 1/2R_{ch,0}$ and $R_{22,0} - R_{ch,0}$ in the ranges where they are approximately constant yields the following estimates: $\hat{a}_{sum,0} = 14.3678 \Omega$, $\hat{a}_{12,0} = 6.9144 \Omega$, $\hat{a}_{22,0} = 13.9376 \Omega$. Finally, one obtains: $R_{G,0} = 7.4535 \Omega$, $R_{S,0} = 6.9140 \Omega$ and $R_{D,0} = 7.0230 \Omega$.

Notice that a rather good agreement was obtained among the $R_{ch,0}$ models based on $R_{sum,0}$, $R_{12,0}$ and $R_{22,0}$, as shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 7. In case of small discrepancies, $R_{22,0}$ is the most indicated for the fitting, as observed in Section 4. Also notice, from the top plot of the figure, that $R_{j,0}$ follows the expected diode low, at least for V_{GS} values such that the extracted $R_{j,0}$ is reliable.

Figure 4: $2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ device from D004IH process. Extracted $R_{sum,0}$ (thick line) with relevant fittings by pseudo-inversion (cross markers) and by least squares (dot markers), plus estimate of $R_{G,0} + R_{S,0}$ (thin line).

6.2 Resistance extraction on 100 nm and 60 nm GaN HEMTs

After developing the presented method on OMMIC's D004IH process, further experiments were carried out by the Authors. In particular, two GaN-based technologies realized by the same foundry were characterized, namely D01GH and D006GH, differing in gate length (100 nm and 60 nm, respectively). The normalized resistances and fittings of two $4 \times$ devices from these technologies are reported respectively in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. As expected, one finds flatter and flatter traces when shifting the focus from $R_{22,0}$ to $R_{12,0}$, to $R_{sum,0}$. Also, notice that the estimates $\hat{a}_{sum,0}$, $\hat{a}_{12,0}$ and $\hat{a}_{22,0}$ are remarkably flat.

In the case of D01GH and D006GH technologies, two full device families have been subjected to the proposed approach, namely 4-finger HEMTs with $W_u = 35, 50, 70, 100 \mu\text{m}$

Figure 5: $2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ device from D004IH process. Extracted $R_{12,0}$ (thick line) with relevant fittings by pseudo-inversion (cross markers) and by least squares (dot markers), plus estimate of $R_{S,0}$ (thin line).

and $W_u = 25, 35, 50, 70 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. As expected, the unnormalized drain and source extrinsic conductances, shown in Fig. 10, are found to vary roughly linearly with W_u . Consequently, the normalized source and drain resistances are very similar among different devices from the same technology. In particular, the average and standard deviation obtained for the D01GH devices are:

- $R_{S,0} = (0.8080 \pm 0.0191) \Omega$
- $R_{D,0} = (1.8427 \pm 0.0378) \Omega$

while for the D006GH:

- $R_{S,0} = (0.8602 \pm 0.0528) \Omega$
- $R_{D,0} = (1.6717 \pm 0.0364) \Omega$

As to the gate conductance, its dependence on W_u (N is implicitly considered fixed) can be modeled as the sum of three contributions [14, 26]:

- residual resistance $R_{G,const}$ (constant term);
- classical expression: $R_{G,lin}W_u$ (proportional term);

Figure 6: $2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ device from D004IH process. Extracted $R_{22,0}$ (thick line) with relevant fittings by pseudo-inversion (cross markers) and by least squares (dot markers), plus estimate of $R_{D,0} + R_{S,0}$ (thin line).

- contact resistance: $R_{G,inv}/W_u$ (inversely proportional term).

The unnormalized R_G of the two device families in D01GH and D006GH technologies is reported in Fig. 11 and is consistent with the above three-term model.

7 Conclusion

This contribution has reappraised some classical results on the analysis of open-channel MESFETs and then presented a new approach for the determination of the extrinsic resistances of a HEMT. Instead of relying on iterative optimizations, this approach makes extensive use of matrix pseudo-inversion to derive a complete low-frequency characterization of the gate junction and of the channel. Also, approximations in the limit (whether in frequency or in gate bias) are thoroughly avoided: no specific resonances or very low/high frequencies are required, and the device always operates at open channel in safe conditions. Finally, the method does not require that the channel should satisfy particular conditions (e.g., symmetry) nor that a full, scaling family should be available.

The first half of the approach (i.e., removing the gate junction) can be applied to

Figure 7: $2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ device from D004IH process. Top: linear fitting to determine I_0 and η by pseudo-inversion. Bottom: fittings of $R_{ch,0}$ based on $R_{sum,0}$, $R_{12,0}$ and $R_{22,0}$.

traditional MESFETs and HEMTs alike. On the contrary, the second half (i.e., modeling the channel resistance as a function of V_{GS}') has been specifically developed to address HEMTs, as a counterpart of the existing MESFET-oriented methods.

The new approach is validated by examples of application to both GaAs- and GaN-based technologies fabricated by OMMIC: advanced processes with 40-nm (D004IH) as well as 100-nm and 60-nm (D01GH and D006GH), respectively, have been selected to the purpose.

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Figure 8: $4 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ device from D01GH process. Extracted $R_{sum,0}$, $R_{12,0}$, $R_{22,0}$ (thick lines) with relevant fittings by pseudo-inversion (cross markers) and by least squares (dot markers), plus estimate of $R_{G,0} + R_{S,0}$, $R_{S,0}$, $R_{D,0} + R_{S,0}$ (thin lines).

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Figure 9: $4 \times 25 \mu\text{m}$ device from D006GH process. Extracted $R_{sum,0}$, $R_{12,0}$, $R_{22,0}$ (thick lines) with relevant fittings by pseudo-inversion (cross markers) and by least squares (dot markers), plus estimate of $R_{G,0} + R_{S,0}$, $R_{S,0}$, $R_{D,0} + R_{S,0}$ (thin lines).

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Figure 10: Extracted G_D (top) and G_S (bottom) from D01GH (cross markers) and D006GH (dot markers) processes as functions of W_u , with $N = 4$.

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Figure 11: Extracted R_G from D01GH (cross markers) and D006GH (dot markers) processes as functions of W_u , with $N = 4$.

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